

Thematic Learning Implementation Multiple Intelligences based Elementary School Character Depok

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Abstract

This research is based on learning that emphasizes the active involvement of learners so that students can gain experience directly and be trained to discover for themselves the knowledge they learn. At that stage, the development of potential learners increases in spiritual and social attitudes, knowledge, and skills necessary for the learners themselves in society and the nation. So that together, the intelligence in the learner will appear and develop. Therefore, paying attention to the development of multiple intelligences is a necessity of thematic learning used as one of the learning models that can adjust to students' learning level, including adjusting the way of learning with the intelligence possessed by each student. Based on this background, the purpose of this research is to know about planning, implementation, and assessment in the thematic learning based on multiple intelligences in Depok Character Elementary School so that it can also be known supporting factors and obstacles in the learning. At the same time, the methodology used in this study is in the form of case study methods by directly observing the phenomena that appear, the situation and condition of the research objects contained in Depok Character Elementary School. Character-Based Holistic Learning Planning (CHLP) to create its module concepts, learning tools, and Electronic Aids that are fun for children—learning with active learning methods that focus on students using brain-based learning, active student learning, contextual learning, cooperative learning, and inquiry-based learning. Therefore, learning is thematic (integrated learning). By applying project-based learning methods in each theme, students are given projects that encourage them to apply their knowledge. Evaluation / Assessment System in thematic learning based on multiple intelligences in Depok Character Elementary School, based on portfolio, presentation of work, essays, self-assessment. Supporting factors and inhibitions in thematic learning based on multiple intelligences in Depok Character Elementary School, namely human resources including educators and educational personnel. Then the facilities are designed with the concept of giving space to explore and blend with nature and cooperation between parents and schools.

Introduction

Technological developments require superior and accomplished human beings to be competent. Efforts to become a human being who is superior and achievers include having intelligence and expertise. Law No. 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System, Chapter 2 Article 3 which states that national education functions to develop abilities (Oppici et al., 2020) and shape the character and civilization of a nation with dignity to educate the life of the nation (Althof & Berkowitz, 2006), aiming to develop the potential of students to become human beings who believe and fear God (Word-Bank, 2017). The one and only, have a noble character, are healthy, knowledgeable, capable, creative, independent and become democratic and responsible citizens. In article 12 paragraph (1) b, every student in each academic unit has the right to receive services according to their talents, interests, and abilities.

Efforts to improve the quality of the process and learning outcomes are carried out by the government, requiring thematic-integrative learning models (Kemendikbud, 2016). One of the most significant implications of implementing the 2013 Curriculum, especially for the Elementary School / *Madrasah Ibtidaiyah* (ES / MI) level, is the use of integrated thematic learning. The thematic learning process provides opportunities for students to develop the potential of students to increase in attitudes (spiritual and social), knowledge, and skills needed for them to live and live in society as a nation and contribute to the welfare of humanity (Hidayah et al., 2020). One of the potentials possessed by every student is intelligence. (Gardner, 2002) states that Intelligence

is the ability to solve problems or create products that are valued within one or more cultural, meaning intelligence is the ability to solve problems or make valuable products in one or more cultures.

Based on information obtained through articles in online media and social networks and an interview with one of the educators at Character Elementary School. The school has been implementing thematic education for more than ten years. The school is one of the favorite schools among the people of Depok and Jakarta. Character schools are public and inclusive schools. The educational facilities provided at this school are pretty complete and provide unique access for students with special needs.

The research problem

1. How is the planning, implementation, and assessment of thematic learning based on multiple intelligences at Cimanggis-Depok Elementary School?
2. What are the supporting and inhibiting factors in thematic learning based on multiple intelligences at Cimanggis-Depok Elementary School?

The objectives of this study

1. To know planning, implementation, and assessment in thematic learning based on multiple intelligences at Cimanggis-Depok Elementary School.
2. To find out the supporting and inhibiting factors in thematic learning based on multiple intelligences at Cimanggis-Depok Elementary School.

Method

This research was conducted through several stages. First, this research will describe the implementation of character education based on multiple intelligence in Cimanggis-Depok Elementary School and the components of planning, implementation, and assessment and supporting and inhibiting factors in its implementation. Second, the research collects data and checks the validity of the data, and concludes. The research flowchart can see in figure 1.

Figure 1. Research Flow

Results and Discussion

The condition of the Covid-19 pandemic so that the research data collection was carried out through online media with the principal of Depok Elementary School on Tuesday, September 15, 2020. The process can be seen in figure 2.

Implementasi Pembelajaran Tematik Berbasis *Multiple Intelligences* di SD Karakter, Cimanggis - Depok

Pengambilan Data Lapangan Penelitian

Sesi Wawancara dengan Kepala SD Karakter (ibu Yulia Pratiwi, S.Pd)
Selasa, 15 September 2020

Pembuka dan Perkenalan

Kepala SD Karakter (Ibu Yulia Pratiwi, S.Pd)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tempat, tanggal lahir: Bogor, 13 Juli 1986 • Status: Berkeluarga, ibu dengan 2 putra • Pendidikan: S1 Bahasa Inggris UNJ • Sedang menempuh S2, jurusan Manajemen Pendidikan di Universitas Pelta Harapan
Ketua Penelitian (Dipi Pujiyanti, M.Pd)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tempat, tanggal lahir: Kuningan, 17 Januari 1985 • Status: Berkeluarga, ibu dengan 2 putri • Pendidikan: S2 Pendidikan Bahasa Indonesia UNJ • Kepangkatan: AA
Anggota 1 (DR. Hj. Nurrohmatul Amaliyah, M.Pd)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tempat, tanggal lahir: Cirebon, 21 Desember 1972 • Status: Berkeluarga, ibu dengan 2 putri • Pendidikan: S3 Pendidikan Dasar UPI • Kepangkatan: Lektor
Anggota 2/ mahasiswa (Nilah)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tempat, tanggal lahir: Tangerang, 09 April 1996 • Status: Berkeluarga • Pendidikan: S1 Pendidikan Faika UHAMKA • Sedang menyelesaikan Pendidikan S1 Uhamka

DAFTAR PERTANYAAN:

- 1 Siapakah yang pertama kali mencetuskan ide penerapan Pendidikan karakter di sekolah yang ibu pimpin dan apa alasannya/latar belakangnya?
- 2 Kapan dimulainya implementasi Pendidikan karakter berbasis *multiple intelligences* dan bagaimana prosesnya?
- 3 Apa sajakah yang program-program sekolah yang dibuat untuk implementasi Pendidikan karakter berbasis *multiple intelligences* di SD Karakter (*verbal linguistic, logis mathematics, special, musical, kinesthetic, interpersonal, intrapersonal, dan naturalistic*)?
- 4 Apakah seluruh kelas (kelas 1 - 6) telah menerapkan Pendidikan karakter berbasis *multiple intelligences* dan apa yang membedakannya di SD kelas rendah dan SD kelas tinggi?
- 5 Kendala-kendala yang muncul biasanya dari hal apa? dalam implemntasinya (jika ada) atau faktor penyebab munculnya kendala-kendala dalam kelancaran implementasi Pendidikan karakter berbasis *multiple intelligences*?
- 6 Bagaimana cara sekolah dan guru-guru dalam menyikapi dan mengatasi permasalahan yang muncul dalam proses implementasi Pendidikan karakter berbasis *multiple intelligences*?
- 7 Apakah ciri khas SD Karakter?
- 8 promosi sekolah dan proses penerimaan siswa baru (apakah terdapat batas maksimal atau kuota tertentu, berapa kelas dan jumlah siswanya)?
- 9 Apa sajakah prestasi yang telah dicetak oleh lulusan siswa SD Karakter?

*Pertanyaan berkembang sesuai interaksi wawancara

Figure 2. Process Collect Data

The research team interviewed the Principal of Depok Character Elementary School. The research team consists of Chief Researcher DepiPujiyanti, M.Pd, DR. HjNurrohmatulAmaliyah, M.Pd, and students. The interview process is conducted online, as shown in figure 3-7.

**Pertanyaan nomor 1-3
(Depi Pujiyanti dengan Kepala SD Karakter)**

1. Siapakah yang pertama kali mencetuskan ide penerapan Pendidikan karakter di sekolah yang ibu pimpin dan apa alasannya/latar belakangnya?
2. Kapan dimulainya implementasi Pendidikan karakter berbasis *multiple intelligences* dan bagaimana prosesnya?
- Apa sajakah yang program-program sekolah yang dibuat untuk implementasi Pendidikan karakter berbasis *multiple intelligences* di SD Karakter (*verbal linguistic, logis mathematics, special, musical, kinesthetic, interpersonal, intrapersonal, dan naturalistic*)?

Figure 3. Interview no.1 - 3

Pertanyaan nomor 4-6
(DR. Hj. Nurrohmatul Amaliyah, M.Pd dengan Kepala SD Karakter)

4. Apakah seluruh kelas (kelas 1 - 6) telah menerapkan Pendidikan karakter berbasis *multiple intelligences* dan apa yang membedakannya di SD kelas rendah dan SD kelas tinggi?
5. Kendala-kendala yang muncul biasanya dari hal apa? dalam implementasinya (jika ada) atau faktor penyebab munculnya kendala-kendala dalam kelancaran implementasi Pendidikan karakter berbasis *multiple intelligences*?
6. Bagaimana cara sekolah dan guru-guru dalam menyikapi dan mengatasi permasalahan yang muncul dalam proses implementasi Pendidikan karakter berbasis *multiple intelligences*?

Figure 5. Interviews 7-9

Figure 6. Interviews Questions Develop

Figure 7. Google-form Filled by Depok Elementary School Teachers **Planning, Implementation, and Assessment in thematic learning based on multiple intelligences at Depok Elementary School**

The character school has developed since 2000 by the Indonesia Heritage Foundation, which was founded by DR. RatnaMegawangi and DR. Sofyan A. Djalil, from the results of an interview with YuliaPratiwi as the Principal of Character Elementary School, The character school has developed since 2000 by the Indonesia Heritage Foundation which was founded by DR. RatnaMegawangi and DR. Sofyan A. Djalil, from the results of an interview with YuliaPratiwi as the Principal of Character Elementary School, it is known that character

schools apply the CHE learning model, namely character-based holistic education. It is known from the Character School Web that the philosophy of CHE is a learning process that can develop human beings as a whole or holistically whose all dimensions develop in a balanced and optimal manner, including the formation of individual awareness that they are part of the family, school, community, and global community members. Character-based Holistic Education (CHE) is education that develops all human dimensions, not only academic abilities, but also physical, emotional, spiritual, creative, and other aspects of multiple intelligence in a holistic and balanced manner through the development of 9 pillars of character, namely:

- 1) Love God and all of his creation
He loved God Almighty and all His creation, manifested in gratitude and prayer and loving, caring for, caring for nature, and its contents (humans, animals, plants, and the environment).
- 2) Independent, discipline, and responsibility
Independent, which is realized by maximizing all one's abilities to carry out various activities with complete discipline and a sense of responsibility.
- 3) Honest trust and wise words
Honest, which is manifested in speech, does not use or take the rights and property of others and dares to admit mistakes if proven wrong.
Trustworthiness or trustworthiness is manifested by keeping promises, conveying messages, or entrusting them to those who have the right and responsibility.
Word of wisdom is manifested by always keeping good, wise, polite, and honest words without hurting or embarrassing other parties and thinking deeply before uttering words.
- 4) Respect, courtesy, and a good listener
Polite courtesy by getting used to thank you, excuse me, ask for help, ask permission every time you do an activity relevant to these words, and speak politely. A good listener is manifested by paying attention to the other person, staring politely at the other person, and not interrupting the conversation. Respect and obedience are manifested by being respectful towards parents, teachers, leaders, and anyone who should be respected regardless of ethnic background, race, religion, and age and obeying applicable laws and regulations.
- 5) Generous, helpful, and cooperative
Generous and Helpful, which is manifested in being helpful to anyone, sharing in any form for those who need it (not limited to property), prioritizing and providing facilities or comfort to those in need such as parents, older adults, pregnant women, and mothers who bring minor children in public facilities such as when on trains, buses and so on. Cooperation is realized with an open attitude to share tasks and share roles to support each other to achieve common goals.
- 6) Confident, creative, and never give up self-confidence is manifested by the ability to lead, compete healthily, dare to appear, and express positively.
Creativity is manifested by setting goals, dreams, hopes and strive in various specific, unique, and measurable ways to archive goals, dreams and strive to find solutions to problems and challenges faced. Abstinence to give up is a series of confident and creative characters that will encourage someone to fight spirit and survive to archive goals.
- 7) Good, fair leader good, and fair leaders are manifested by the ability to take the initiative to lead, set an example, protect, do good and invite for good and nurture, be fair, admit mistakes if there are any, provide opportunities for others to appear and play a role, open to cooperation and sharing for mutual success.
- 8) Kind, humble kindness, and humility are manifested by behaving respectfully, happy to help, always doing and spreading kindness, apologizing and forgiving, smiling and not boasting.
- 9) Tolerant, love, peace, and unity tolerance are manifested by respecting different backgrounds (ethnicity, race, religion and culture), respecting the beliefs, religions, and places of worship, not imposing one's will, not feeling the most right and good. Love of peace is manifested in behavior that prioritizes peace, apologizes to one another, and is patient. Unity is the embodiment of Tolerance and Love of peace, giving birth to a character that loves unity and unity.

Character Elementary School applies nine pillars of character, hoping that they can form a character within themselves in theory and practice it in everyday life. Indeed his positive character can be transmitted. In the flow of character values according to the results of the interview, it was stated that there were two methods used, namely:

- 1) Special streaming, this particular streaming is for 15-20 minutes a day in the morning. There are times, for example, this month the character taught is the pillar of character 1, namely love of God and all of its creation. The following month the character being taught is, for example, August 17, fitting to teach the character of cooperation or pillar six-character, namely self-confidence, creativity, and never give

up, for example following seventeen. So there is a time when we have plotted what characters will be taught, and then the lesson plan is made either through videos, through stories through games, or through other activities that are special at times.

- 2) Streaming in an integrated manner with learning activities, this integrated means entering into flow in learning when for example, learning the theme of the community is peaceful means that in every learning character values are included in the form of appreciation when students do a task well such as thank you for completing the task or when there is a conflict with friends resolved with the core of the character, for example, accidentally spilling his drinking water. The conflict resolution is through a character like "oh how can his friend be sad, what to do, apologize, besides comforting his heart and helping to refill the spilled drinking water" from the pillar. Please help.

The application of education and learning in thematic learning based on multiple intelligences at Depok Character Elementary School, through:

- DAP (Developmentally Appropriate Practices), the stages of learning according to age
- Active Learning
- Integrated and Thematic
- Brain-based Learning
- Foster curiosity (Inquiry-based learning)
- Contextual
- Learning with real practice
- Learning to work in teams
- Effective classroom management and positive communication

The character education approach in thematic learning based on multiple intelligences at Depok Character Elementary School, through:

- Explicit, systematic, and continuous
- The 3M Method of Kindness (Understanding, Loving and Doing Good)
- Integration of Character and Thematic Pillars in learning centers
- Use of educational games and character-building aids
- Storytelling activities with character series literacy books (more than 120 titles)
- Inviting active involvement of parents

The implementation of thematic learning based on multiple intelligences at Depok Character Elementary School has a Theme Project, a unique activity at the end of learning the theme or the peak of the theme. An example is on special days like August 17 (Independence day) and others. In the implementation of project-based learning, it pays close attention to multiple intelligence, namely respecting the ability and competence of children in any case, for example, there are children whose competence in communication means that later in this project they will get a presentation part, for example there are children whose competence in arithmetic in this project will be optimized to become cashiers, for example When the generous pillar likes to help and cooperate, there is one time from the 5 pillars the goal is that the children make a bazaar for used goods, from used goods that are suitable for use, the children first collect their used goods at home then the children are asked To measure for yourself, how much is the right price for the item he has, so that the child can think creatively, associating if my item is clothes but my clothes are in 90% condition from the parents of students, the purchase price is in the amount of rupiah, the estimate will be sold at the bazaar, how much can it be hook like that then when the children have collected it they label the price themselves and then discuss it with the teacher.

On the day of the bazaar, the students maintain their stand from there, they strategize roughly with bazaar items that are almost the same as bazaar items in other classes, what must be done to be able to sell these bazaar items, that's when the children's ability to think creatively, find solutions to items that are the same then sell how the promotion strategy is needed. So that in addition to practicing cognitive abilities, character building, children also train their multiple intelligences, for children who have good communication are usually advised to promote their items to other classes, then those with good arithmetic mean that are advised to look after the cashier. So project-based character pillar activities that hopefully can explore all the abilities a child has even though one child and another are different but put together in one container and projects like this are not only in the pillar of character but also in learning in themes.

Learning planning, the curriculum used, refers to the 2013 curriculum but is packaged with a Character-Based Holistic learning model to make its module concept and creates its theme in each class from grade 1 to grade 6. For example, in class 2, the first theme is I am an Indonesian child well. My Indonesian child learns various things such as cultural differences, the rights and obligations of citizens. As for the location of the multiple intelligences on this theme, a theme project is made for the goal to be achieved, for example in my theme, Indonesian children, the big goal is that children can recognize various cultures in Indonesia, able to express and

be able to have an attitude of tolerance towards differences that exist in Indonesia. Before this project started, the teachers at the beginning of the theme had informed that the project would carry out later this theme. For example, there was a student presentation, so that each student presented a culture he chose from the presentation to hone their skills.

Each child owns this multiple intelligence, how the teacher accompanies, provides opportunities, and then provides reinforcement so that each of these intelligence characters grows optimally, one of which is training towards the final project theme by making presentations, training their linguistic skills to develop than when the project is others, for example, young entrepreneurs there are trained to develop their arrhythmias. This project is expected that each child will be able to develop on their terms if there are children who like to sing musical, it means that later on this project the children will perform one song, there are children who are linguistic which means that this child in the project will read fairy tales or play roles. For example, during a pandemic, an online project was successfully created, which was the work of a 2nd-grade elementary school, namely the Festival Nusantara. In this archipelago culture, the children sang, danced playing dramas that were done at home and then edited so that they could become one view. a show that can be watched by all parents of the students themselves and other classes. The projects carried out in each theme can help children hone their abilities. The teachers facilitate so that they do not only read books and then work on worksheets but also carry out various project activities to train their abilities.

The implementation of learning in each class is accompanied by two teachers, namely the core teacher and the accompanying teacher. Mapping was carried out in each level, and the mapping referred to includes gender, cognitive abilities, social and emotional abilities. In the lower class, what is built is a love of learning by doing concrete and practical activities. The enthusiasm for learning is built so that later, in grades 4, 5 and 6 there are no longer children who do not want to learn they already love. In the core learning activity, the teacher flows learning using methods that have been designed in the lesson plan. Thematic learning provides opportunities for children to learn more contextually and actively by providing examples that occur around students and using very focused methods on student activeness such as discussions, role playing, group work, and others. Then the learning activity is closed by concluding the lesson and providing feedback.

The learning process has two forms of teaching: character education integrated with the subjects and specifically through the streaming pillars of character. For example, there are three central values in Islam, namely morals, manners, and exemplary. All three are applied to implement thematic learning based on multiple intelligence with a character-based holistic learning model. Based on the interview results, the pattern of implementing character education is integrated with the subjects. This includes mentioning the character values contained therein, integrating character values directly into the subject, inserting them into the questions given by the teacher when giving praise, using parables with events experienced. In addition, students use stories to bring out character values and integrate character values by using activities such as social service, field trips, home visits, outbound, and activities that can bring out human values.

The Evaluation / Assessment System in thematic learning based on multiple intelligences at Depok Character Elementary School, based on portfolios, presentation of work results, essays, self-assessment. The assessment from grades 1-4 is in the form of a narrative. In grade 5, the assessment is in the form of narratives and numbers, but these numbers are not shown to students because they are worried that it will reduce students' enthusiasm. Especially for grade 6, there will be a deepening of the material in semester 2. For example, for children who still need help in learning mathematics after school, they will gather with their friends and teachers to deepen mathematics material and science or other subjects. Semester 1 focuses on materials, while semester two has focused on learning that you want to test. But when there are no more national examinations, what must be developed is basic life competencies or more essential.

Supporting and inhibiting factors in thematic learning based on multiple intelligences at Depok Character Elementary School

Supporting and inhibiting factors include:

a) Human Resources

Human resources include educators and education personnel, teachers in schools are teachers who are recruited after going through various stages of recruitment, such as interviews with school directors or with foundation directors, after having to go through several essay tests to explore further the character of the teacher, which is focused on his childhood and his daily relationships with family. Then the next one is the English language test and others. After that, the most important thing is when it is the first time you join a character school, there is a name called MOKARU. This MOKARU is a teacher character orientation period that lasts for three months. During these three months, the teachers receive training on character education, how to flow learning, techniques for communication in children, conflict resolution techniques, fun math, and thematic fun for three months. After graduating from the 3-month orientation period, he officially joined a character school when he saw this suitable teacher. So there is a school that

is a teacher before entering the classroom. This is done to maintain the quality of thematic learning based on multiple intelligences at Depok Character Elementary School. The Teacher Competencies that must be possessed are: 1) High Spirit Teaching Able to build a pleasant learning environment and motivated students; 2) Positive and effective communication and interaction with students and parents Able to create an atmosphere of peace and courtesy and a sense of being loved, respected, valued, understood, the unique abilities of each student; 3) Cultivate an Attitude of Tolerance Has a tolerance for differences in culture, ethnicity, religion and arises mutual respect and understanding; 4) Motivator for students Responding to failure as the best learning opportunity and not giving up The key to the success of implementing this model is the ability of teachers, so for schools wishing to apply this model, IHF requires teachers to attend training for 15 days, because with this training teachers are prepared to have a paradigm, a sense of mission, and a burning spirit to become teachers who character. To prepare competent teachers, teachers need to be equipped with practical theories, primarily how to distribute them in the classroom.

In addition to pleasant conditions, teachers must have knowledge and skills in teaching methods. PAUD *SemaiBenihBangsa* applies the educational methods we need, such as Brain-based Learning, Contextual Learning, Cooperative Learning, Inquiry-based Learning, Developmentally Appropriate Practices, etc. The teachers are provided with training to master these methods practically. IHF has provided training to teachers in more than 1600 PAUD and kindergartens, where the material provided is a standard as described as follows: 1) Theory about the Importance of Character Education; 2) Theory and Implementation of Education with the 9 Pillars of Character explicitly; knowing the good; 3) reasoning the good, feeling the good, and acting the good; 4) Principles and application of Brain-based Learning; 5) Application of Developmentally Appropriate Practices (DAP); 6) Application of Multiple Intelligences; 7) Principles and Application of Character-based Integrated Learning; 8) Principles and Applications of Cooperative Learning; 9) Positive and Effective Communication; 10) Principles and Application of Student Active Learning, Contextual Learning, and Project-Based Learning; 11) Eight Principles of Learning to Read fun (whole language, Environmental Prints, etc); 12) Principles and Application of Inquiry-based Learning; 13) Fun Story Telling; 14) Class Management; 15) Implementation of the Sentra system (there are 7 centers); 16) Character-based Co-Parenting; and 17) Motivation Training.

- b) Facilities Following the CHE philosophy, the Character School Building was designed with the concept of providing space for exploration and being one with nature. Apart from that, what is given, teachers must also be provided with teaching aids, such as modules, curricula, lesson plans, educational games, and storybooks. Without these tools, it will be difficult for teachers to apply the knowledge they have learned. There are also teaching aids provided by IHF, which are: 1) Module 9 Character Pillars; 2) Daily Lesson Plan for 9 Pillars of Character; 3) KTSP Module for Character-Based Holistic Education by Themes; 4) Daily Lesson Plan for learning centers; 5) 9 Pillars Character Book Package for student activities (10 books); 6) The storybooks make up the 9 Pillars of Character (125 books) 7. Character-Based Holistic Education textbooks; 7) Educational games and center equipment Ppkages (70 types); 8) 9 Pillar Character Songs Package (60 songs), and 9) Moral Establishment CD Package.
- c) Parents are actively involved in efforts to develop children's character. One of the success factors of character education is the consistency between school and home regarding implementing the character pillars that are instilled. Character Elementary School always holds outreach regarding the vision / mission and educational philosophy applied at the Character School, both before parents register their children and their children. At the beginning of the new school year, the school requires parents to attend seminars held by the school. In addition, the school periodically holds parenting education seminars. This is done so that parents understand parenting practices that are harmful to children's character development. Parents are also encouraged to read books published by IHF, including the Character Education Series books, which provide instructions on installing characters in children. The existence of this collaboration turns out to be many parents who claim to have learned a lot about how to be good parents, and even feel that their character is getting better, and learn a lot about noble moral behavior from their children. School collaboration with parents must be strong in a way that parents are actively involved. Parents' support is carried out with parenting events and super day events for parents of grade 6 students who will continue to not panic in facing the National Examination. The Character-Based Parenting Training / Seminar / Workshop includes: (a). Brain-based Parenting 1) Love-based parenting for optimal child development 2) The importance of the first 1000 days of the child 3) Brain-Friendly Parenting to install Child Character 4) Forming Mother-Child Attachment: The Key to a Healthy, Intelligent and Creative Soul. (b). Neuroscience in Character Development 1) Correlation of the Brain Work System with Emotional Control 2) Parenting and Education Patterns that give birth to a Creative Generation 3) Positive communication to form children's character 4) Child Moral Development Stage. (c). Challenges of Parenting Children in the Digital Age 1) Understand and Overcome the Impact of Video Games (violence or pornography) 2) Protection of children from the dangers of violence. (d).

Motivation 1) Being an Idol Parent. (e). Child Nutrition and Development 1) The importance of nutrition and immunization in children's mental and physical development.

Character education is very well applied to the age of primary education. Children are in the Golden Age, which must be given positive knowledge, need direction towards kindness, and create a pleasant and comfortable learning atmosphere. Character education is to install character values and develop children's cognitive values and develop children's multiple intelligence. The application of character education can be made by inserting character values in the learning process, starting with the teacher as a role model to imitate the character values developed. The learning model used is the Character-based Holistic Learning model. The curriculum used is the Character-based Integrated Curriculum, an integrated curriculum that "touches" children's needs, which aims to develop all human dimensions. As previously described, a human with character is a human being who develops all its dimensions as a whole (holistically) so that this human can be called holy (holy and wise).

The root of the word holy is whole, so the meaning of holy man is a human who develops in a comprehensive and balanced manner (Megawangi, 2007). The aim is to develop a holistic/whole person (whole person) who is capable of facing a world that is full of challenges and rapidly changing and has an emotional and spiritual awareness that he is part of the whole (the person within a whole). Learning planning is designed in such a way as to create models, learning tools, and fun electronic teaching aids for children. RPP learning plans in multiple intelligence learning are called lesson plans (Ary et al., 2010; Liu et al., 2020; Snowman & McCown, 2015). The curriculum is structured based on the principle of the relationship between learning materials, compartmentalized, and can reflect dimensions and skills by displaying interesting and contextual themes (Fortner et al., 2016; Ireland et al., 2012; Koksal & Berberoglu, 2014; Suryawati & Osman, 2018; Tan, 2017). Development fields in kindergarten and existing subjects in Elementary School and Junior High School which are developed in the concept of education life skills related to personal and social education, development thinking / cognitive, character development, and motor perception development can also be woven well if the teaching material is designed through integrated learning and thorough (Holistic) (Donohoe, 2019; Meterbayeva et al., 2015; Yoders, 2014). Holistic learning occurs when the curriculum can display different themes encourage exploration or events authentically and naturally (Cárdenas-Robledo & Peña-Ayala, 2019; Schuler, 2014; Temmen & Friederic, 2016). With the emergence of this natural theme or event, a process will occur meaningful learning, and the material design will be interrelated with various fields of development in the curriculum. An example of thematic learning assessment at Character Elementary School Depok is presented in a theme project in figure 8.

My Indonesian Children's Theme Project in the form of My Indonesia Booklet and appearance2 in Gebyar Budaya Nusantara

My Indonesian Booklet by grade 2 students can be viewed and accessed on the Character School web <http://sekolahkarakter.sch.id/buku-kecil-indonesiaku/>

Gebyar Budaya Nusantara*

 SD Karakter Tapos
<https://youtu.be/ISMDYjPoLoE>

 SD Karakter Cimanggis
<https://youtu.be/TVaCrUOtuk>

Please help the video is only used for research needs.

Figure 8. Thematic Learning

Implementation of Depok Character Elementary School Student Theme Project. The implementation of learning uses the active learning method, which focuses on students as mentioned by (Faujiah et al., 2018) in their research that character schools use brain-based learning, active student learning, contextual learning, cooperative learning, and inquiry-based learning methods. Thematic learning (integrated learning) by applying the project-based learning method (in each theme, students are given projects are encouraging them to apply

their knowledge). The intelligence developed in multiple intelligence in character-based holistic education based on Gardner in his book *Frame of The Mind* includes (Gardner, 2002):

1. Verbal-linguistic intelligence (word smart), namely the ability to think in words and use language to express and appreciate complex meanings.
2. Logical-mathematical intelligence (intelligent numbers) can calculate, measure, and consider propositions and hypotheses and complete mathematical operations (Jayantika et al., 2013).
3. Visual-spatial intelligence (color-image intelligence), that is, awakens the capacity to think in three-dimensional ways. This intelligence enables a person to perceive external and internal images, repaint, change, or modify images, drive oneself and objects through a room, and generate or decipher graphic information (Fink et al., 2002).
4. Musical intelligence (intelligent music songs) is visible in someone who has sensitivity to pitch, melody, rhythm, and tone patterns (Helmbold et al., 2005).
5. Kinesthetic intelligence (intelligent movement) allows a person to move objects and subtle physical skills (Wang, 2015).
6. Interpersonal intelligence (social intelligence) can understand and interact with other people effectively (Pérez et al., 2017).
7. Intrapersonal intelligence can make accurate perceptions of oneself and use such knowledge in planning and directing one's life.
8. Naturalist intelligence (natural intelligence), namely intelligent naturalists who appear to be lovers of animals and plants, is sensitive to nature (Schuler, 2014).
9. Existential intelligence (essence intelligence), namely the ability to think about something essential, concerning the existence of various things, including life-death, good-evil (Cárdenas-Robledo & Peña-Ayala, 2019).

Looking at all aspects that are applied in the Character Elementary School, this is following the opinion of (Haryanto & Akhirin, 2018), which states that there are four steps for character building, namely (1) including character concepts in every learning activity by instilling the value of kindness to children, using methods that make children have a reason or desire to do good, develop an attitude of loving good deeds, and perform good deeds; (2) making slogans that can foster good habits in the behavior of the school community; (3) continuous monitoring; and (4) parental assessment.

According to (Jhon, 2021), the goal of the Character-Based Holistic Education model is to form a whole human (holistic) with character, namely to develop the physical, emotional, social, creative, spiritual, and intellectual aspects of students optimally, and to form people who are life long learners. Although, as for the comparison from other schools, there are still many that have not implemented this character education pattern, there are still many schools that focus only on knowledge, not on feelings and practices.

Learning evaluation in measuring competency attainment is carried out using a portfolio system (Hunter-Johnson & Closson, 2012). The portfolio system tools are (1) evaluation of daily learning activities; (2) evaluation at the end of each lesson; (3) a collection of children's work; and (4) anecdotal record. Character Elementary School does not hold final semester exams. Assessment by the teacher is carried out following the indicators of competency achievement. The teacher assesses numbers, but the value given to students is in the form of narratives or words. The parents are informed about the overall achievement of competencies in the form of report, six potential aspects need to be developed through education, namely (Idris et al., 2012).

- 1) Physical aspects, namely aspects related to optimal gross and fine motoric development.
- 2) Emotional aspects, namely aspects related to mental health aspects, being able to control stress, self-control from negative actions, self-confidence, dare to take risks, and empathy.
- 3) Social and cultural aspects, namely aspects related to learning to enjoy work, working in teams, being good at socializing, caring about social problems and having a social spirit, being responsible, respecting others, understanding cultural differences and other people's habits, complying with all regulations apply.
- 4) Aspects of creativity, namely aspects related to the ability to express oneself in various productive activities (music, thoughts, etc.), as well as finding the right solutions to various problems.
- 5) The spiritual aspect is the ability to interpret the meaning and purpose of life and be able to reflect on himself, knowing his mission in this life as an essential part of a living system and behaving *ta'azim* to all of God's creation; and
- 6) Academic aspects, namely aspects related to logical thinking, language, and writing well. In addition, it can raise critical questions and conclude from various known information.

In improving service quality as a determining factor for success to be achieved in thematic learning based on multiple intelligences at Depok Character Elementary School, it is very concerned about Human Resources (HR) quality, namely the quality of the employees they have. Although according to (Davies & West-Burnham, 2016), teaching resources and education personnel are significant and are the spearhead in the process of providing educational services to students in institutions, there are several examples of services provided by educators and education personnel, namely teaching techniques not monotonous, technological skills, English

proficiency (one part of the expertise that the teacher must master), fun teaching methods, safe use of APE, giving motivation and praise that uses positive sentences and does not lead to physical praise, and getting used to does not give labels to students, examples of labels in question (lazy, stupid, and so on), creates a comfortable and loving environment that exists among employees and even for guests, it feels very comfortable and full of love.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the study, it was concluded that:

1. Learning planning, the curriculum used, refers to the 2013 curriculum but is packaged with a character-based Holistic learning model to create their module concepts, learning tools, and fun electronic teaching aids for children.
2. Implementation of learning using a character-based Holistic learning model with active learning methods that focus on students using brain-based learning methods, active student learning, contextual learning, cooperative learning, and inquiry-based learning. Thematic learning (integrated learning) by applying the project-based learning method in each theme, students are given projects that encourage them to apply their knowledge).
3. Evaluation / Assessment System in thematic learning based on multiple intelligences at Depok Character Elementary School, based on theme projects, portfolios, presentation of work results, essays, self-assessment. The teacher assesses numbers, but the value given to students is in the form of narratives or words. The parents are informed about the overall achievement of competencies in the form of report cards.
4. Supporting and inhibiting factors in thematic learning based on multiple intelligences at Depok Character Elementary School, namely human resources including educators and educational staff. Then the facilities are designed with the concept of providing space for exploration and blending with nature and cooperation between parents and school.

Recommendations

The recommendation in this study is that there is a need for a more in-depth study of the Student-Centered Learning-based curriculum learning model developed in elementary schools.

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